

Metal Complexes of Salicylidene-O-Aminophenol

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Manuscript received 10 May 1977, revised 28 August 1978, accepted 8 September 1978

The composition of Ce(IV), Th(IV), UO₂(II), and Fe(III) complexes of salicylidene-O-aminophenol in solution have been determined by conductometric and spectrophotometric methods. The complexes of Ce(IV) and Th(IV) could be isolated in the solid form, analysed chemically and their structures were determined on the basis of I. R. studies and conductance measurements.

THE structures and characteristics of the fluorescent metal chelates of salicylidene-*o*-aminophenol have been studied¹. The reagent has also been used for spectrofluorimetric determination of aluminium². This communication deals with the composition, and structure of Ce(IV), Th(IV), UO₂(II), and Fe(III) complexes of the reagent.

Experimental

Physical methods—as reported earlier^{3,4}

Reagents and Solutions—Ceric ammonium nitrate, thorium nitrate, uranyl acetate, ferric nitrate and all other reagents used were of A. R. grade. Salicylidene-*o*-aminophenol was synthesized by the condensation of salicylaldehyde and *o*-aminophenol as described earlier¹ and its solution was prepared in acetone. All the other solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Results and Discussion

The pH titrations of the mixture of metal ion and ligand in the ratio 1 : 0, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 with 0.1M NaOH indicated a downward shift in the pH from 1 : 0 to 1 : 1 in the case of all the metals showing the liberation of hydrogen ions during the complex ion formation. Blank titration with the ligand had no effect upon the titration curves described above.

The spectrophotometric studies were carried out only in the case of Ce(IV), UO₂(II) and Fe(III) as no sharp colour change was observed in the case of other metal ion. Application of the method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁵ to the system M : Ligand (in the ratio of 4 : 1, 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 4, keeping total volume 20 ml) demonstrated the existence of one complex in each case. As the ligand also absorbs strongly at the maxima of the complex, i.e., 420 nm, the wavelength selected for giving the maximum difference between the absorbance of complex and ligand were 520, 570 and 600 nm for the complex of Fe(III), Ce(IV) and UO₂(II) respectively.

Job's method⁶ was used to determine the composition of the complexes. Equimolar solutions

of the reactants at two different concentrations (0.0033M, 0.005M) were used. Molar ratio method⁷ was also used to find out the composition of the complexes. The pH of the mixtures was maintained approximately 3.5, 4.5 and 4.0 in the case of Fe(III), UO₂(II) and Ce(IV) respectively by the addition of NaOH or HCl. These methods including slope ratio⁸ and the method of Bent and French⁹ showed the formation of 1:1 complex in each case.

The combining ratio was further confirmed by conductometric titrations (20 ml of the ligand of conc. 0.03M and 0.05M in the cell).

Isolation of the Complexes : Only Ce(IV) and Th(IV) complexes could be isolated in the solid form. These were prepared by mixing equimolar solutions (0.01M) of the reactants. The pH of the mixture was adjusted 9.0 and 4.1 in the case of Ce(IV) and Th(IV) respectively by the addition of NaOH and then the mixture were allowed to stand overnight. The yellowish crystals formed were filtered, washed several times with distilled water and dried in desiccator. As long as the complexes do not exist in the hydroxo form, they remain in solution. They were analysed chemically for the metal ion, carbon and hydrogen.

[Ce(C₁₃H₉O₂N)(OH)₂(H₂O)] Found Ce, 34.55%; C, 37.92%; H, 3.09%; Calc. Ce, 34.75% C, 38.70%; H, 3.22%

[Th(C₁₃H₉O₂N)(OH)₂(H₂O)] Found Th, 46.54%; C, 31.45%; H, 2.56%; Calc., Th, 46.86%; C, 31.70% H, 2.64%

The values of molar conductance in nitrobenzene (5.8 and 8.9 mhos) indicated their non-electrolytic nature.

I. R. studies : The main characteristic feature of the I. R. spectra was a shift in the position of νC=N band from 1630 cm⁻¹ in the ligand to 1610⁻¹ and 1600 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of Th(IV) and Ce(IV) complexes respectively. The OH band observed at 3480 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of ligand also shifted to 3400 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of complexes. This band was of strong intensity and broad due to the combined effect of coordinated OH and H₂O. A weak band observed at 480 cm⁻¹ may be assigned

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to a combined frequency arising from M-O and M-N linkage.

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